

This overview refers to the paper "Electron Geometry". The first two pages of the paper show a possible toroidal geometry to model electrons. Three lengths associated with the electron can also be associated with the geometry of a self-intersecting circular torus. I refer to these lengths as the electron radii, which is common for the classical radius and Bohr radius. The Compton radius is commonly known as the reduced Compton wavelength. Toroidal electron models have been tried for a long time, but I haven't seen this particular geometry described before.

The torus defining the geometry is defined by two radii, beta and gamma. The algebraic derivation isn't shown, but the calculations on page 2 for beta and gamma show that they are derived from the Compton radius and the fine-structure constant alpha. The intersection at the center of the electron orbit is very small - the electron classical radius gives half the width of the self-intersection.

The proposed electron is comprised of a quantum, treated as a sphere of radius r as shown in Fig 1, traversing a circular helical **orbit** that wraps around a toroidal surface. The radius r is calculated to be roughly **2.0E-19 meter**. The torus is not physical, it defines the shape of the geometry. The electron then is mostly empty space. In an atom, the nucleus would be at the center of such electrons, and the Bohr radius is also the outermost radius of the electron orbit. The electron classical radius is roughly 13850 times larger than the moving spherical quantum.

The pitch of the helix, analogous to a thread pitch, is not yet determined by the model. It would be determined by the speed of the moving quantum.

Given the two chiralities possible for a toroidal helix, the geometry is a natural fit with the existence of matter and anti-matter. The toroidal helix is taken here to be a circular helical curve confined to the surface of a self-intersecting torus.

I am assuming even free electrons have these orbits - that somehow it is a stable geometry. Maybe interacting with the Higgs field leads to stable orbits.

From Wikipedia: "The Higgs field is a field of energy that is thought to exist in every region of the universe. The field is accompanied by a fundamental particle known as the Higgs boson, which is used by the field to continuously interact with other particles, such as the electron. Particles that interact with the field are "given" mass..."

A 5 page PDF is available at Zenodo. Calculations in the paper lead to some numerical matches that may not be viable since they currently depend on the choice of units used in the paper.